

Multiplexed PSF engineering for 3D multicolor particle tracking

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Abstract

Three-dimensional spatiotemporal tracking of microscopic particles in multiple colors is a challenging optical imaging task. Existing approaches require a trade-off between photon-efficiency, field of view, mechanical complexity, spectral specificity and speed. Here, we introduce multiplexed point-spread-function engineering that achieves photon efficient, 3D, multicolor particle tracking over a large field of view. This is accomplished by first chromatically splitting the emission path of a microscope to different channels, engineering the point-spread function of each, and then recombining them onto the same region of the camera. We demonstrate our technique for simultaneously tracking five types of emitters in-vitro, as well as co-localization of DNA loci in live yeast cells.

Introduction

Tracking individual fluorescent probes with nanoscale precision has many biological applications, including characterization of membrane dynamics¹, DNA replication and repair, gene expression and regulation^{2,3}, RNA structure^{4,5}, and protein folding⁶. Individual trajectories of fluorescently labelled biomolecules have provided insights into their behavior and environment^{7,8}. Importantly, the interaction between two or more biomolecules is of key interest^{9,10} necessitating multicolor imaging.

In high numerical-aperture (NA) optical systems, imaging suffers from a shallow depth of field of several hundred nanometers; outside of this range, emitters appear blurry and dim, resulting in poor localization precision. This fundamental limitation has driven the emergence of various methods to enable 3D tracking. Notable techniques such as light sheet microscopy^{11,12} and confocal laser-scanning microscopy (CLSM)¹³ have been shown to provide advantages in resolution and signal to noise ratio (SNR), however, they require a scanning procedure, which inherently impairs temporal resolution, making them sub-optimal for imaging fast, dynamic scenes.

Scan-free methods for 3D single particle tracking (SPT) include interference-based imaging, multiplane imaging, feedback-control, and point-spread-function engineering (PSFE). Interference-based methods extract the 3D position of an emitter from an interference pattern usually generated by collecting light using two objective lenses. This exquisitely sensitive approach is typically limited to a small axial range of several hundreds of nanometers due to the ambiguity associated with interference of visible light^{14,15}. In multiplane imaging, light from the sample is split to form images corresponding to multiple focal planes, providing simultaneous views of emitters in several nominal focal planes. Due to splitting the light into multiple images, the field of view (FOV) is restricted in order for each depth to fit side-by-side on a single camera sensor^{16,17}, or multiple cameras are required¹⁸. Feedback-controlled methods are usually characterized by exceptionally high spatial and temporal resolution, but are typically limited to tracking a single particle at a time, or to a very small FOV^{19–21}.

In PSFE, a special phase mask in the pupil plane is used to modify the wavefront originating from a point source, such that 3D information is encoded in the shape of the PSF^{22–24}. This enables scan-free 3D

localization by subsequent computational image analysis. An important aspect relevant to all mentioned methods is that for achieving optimal resolution, the optical system must be highly photon-efficient; in localization microscopy, the Poisson-distributed nature of light dictates that localization precision scales as the inverse square-root of the photon count, at best^{25–27}.

Of key interest in many particle tracking experiments is measuring the relative motions of two or more types of particles, which can be accomplished by conjugating labels with unique spectra and performing multicolor imaging. Sensitive detectors (cameras) in fluorescence microscopy are typically monochrome, therefore the straightforward way to obtain spectral information is to perform sequential image acquisition, naturally entailing a decrease in temporal resolution. Alternatively, it is possible to preserve temporal resolution by sacrificing FOV, either by assigning different FOVs to different spectral channels^{9,28,29}, or by acquiring a designated spectral imaging channel alongside a spatial imaging channel^{30,31}. This approach is photon-efficient and enables simultaneous multicolor acquisition, but significantly reduces the FOV, or is costly and space-consuming due to the necessity of multiple cameras²⁹.

Extracting spectral and depth information while minimizing temporal and spatial penalty has been previously demonstrated using color-dependent PSFs that encode the colors of emitters while maintaining the benefits of PSFE³². Phase modulation was implemented by a liquid crystal spatial light modulator (LC-SLM) generating a single, wavelength-dependent phase mask (see also^{33,34}) yielding two different PSFs for two specified spectral bands. While this approach proved successful for discriminating two colors, a photon-efficient extension to three or more colors remains a difficult task using commercially available LC-SLMs. This is due to three main reasons – first, a large dynamic phase range is required; second, the polarization dependency of the LC-SLM entails ~50% photon-loss for typical, unpolarized, fluorescence; third, the broad emission spectra of most fluorescent molecules are incompatible with the strong wavelength-dependence necessary for a three-color phase mask.

An alternative for LC-SLMs are diffractive optical elements (DOEs). Single-color DOEs can be fabricated by photolithography³⁵, however a wavelength-dependent DOE for multicolor PSFE is challenging to fabricate due to the requirement for a large etching depth range with nanoscale precision. The benefit of encoding spectral characteristics into the PSF optimized for 3D tracking makes it worthwhile to pursue methods to bypass the technical limitations posed by the multicolor LC-SLM or DOE.

Here, we introduce multiplexed PSFE: a method for photon-efficient multicolor 3D SPT over a large FOV that combines multiple color-specific engineered PSFs onto a single imaging channel. The concept of the method is to use simple, single-color DOEs while generating a detectable difference between the PSFs of different colors to provide multicolor detection. Importantly, photon loss is low, as the major sources of photon loss in existing large-FOV multicolor PSFE are circumvented. This yields video-rate imaging of molecular probes with precision down to tens of nanometers. We demonstrate our method by simultaneous 3D tracking of five spectrally distinct populations of diffusing beads and DNA loci in live yeast cells.

Results

We achieve multiplexed PSFE for multicolor 3D-SPT by first splitting the image into three spectral channels using dichroic beamsplitters. Next, PSFE is performed separately in each channel, and finally the channels are recombined at the camera sensor plane. In traditional PSFE systems, the camera is positioned downstream of a 4-f extension to the optical path to access the Fourier-plane of the optical system. This enables phase modulation of the pupil function by placing a carefully-aligned phase mask in the Fourier plane. In our setup, the extra available space along the extended optical path is also used for spectral separation in addition to PSFE (Figure 1.a). Consequently, both the color and 3D position of a point source are encoded by the shape of the PSF.

In our work, we use masks that are optimized for 3D localization over a defined axial range. The optimized PSFs have the same forms as Tetrapod PSF family³⁶, thus benefit from the PSFs appearing significantly different upon rotation of the phase mask by small angles (Figure 1.b). This enables the use of three similar-shaped phase masks at different lateral angles to generate efficient and easily distinguishable PSFs. Throughout the paper, the three channels are referred to as blue, orange and red, corresponding the perceived color of their spectral transmission bands upon white-light illumination.

To demonstrate the concept, we tracked freely-diffusing fluorescent beads with five different spectral emission profiles, at a high framerate of 50 fps. To our knowledge, 3D tracking of >3 distinct particle populations at high spatiotemporal resolution was not previously performed over a large volume. We were able to classify more than three spectrally unique bead types by incorporating inter-channel ratiometric

information. The beads were freely diffusing in a water-glycerol mixture and simultaneously imaged at video-rate for tracking (Figure 2). A short exposure time (20 ms) was used to motion-blur.

Figure 1. The optical system. **(a)** A simplified schematic drawing of the optical system. Fluorescence of multiple spectral bands is emitted from the sample forming a colorful image at the intermediate image plane. Subsequently, a 4-f system is used to both divide the light into three spectral channels by dichroics and perform PSFE per channel. Abbreviations: Ex. - excitation illumination, Em. - Emitted fluorescence, D, D1, D2- Dichroic beamsplitters, M - mirror, TL - tube lens, L1, L2 - lenses of the 4-f system, IIP - intermediate image plane, FIP - final image plane (Note: Several mirrors were excluded from the drawing, for clarity. See Figure S1 for full details). **(b)** Concept of PSFE - by introducing a phase mask at the pupil plane, depth is encoded by the shape of the PSF as measured in the final image plane. A simulated comparison between the standard PSF (top row) and the 4-μm Tetrapod PSF (bottom row) is shown. The PSFs are of a sub-diffraction emitter placed at five different axial positions relative to the nominal focal plane (NFP). The orientation of the PSF is directly determined by the orientation of the phase pattern at the pupil, here presented tilted at roughly $\pi/6$. **(c)** A representation of the phase masks placed at the pupil plane. Each mask is uniquely oriented to produce a channel-specific PSFs.

As expected from their emission spectra, two of the beads types were clearly visible in more than one channel: Crimson Fluospheres (emission peak at 645 nm) appeared in the orange and red channels, and Tetraspeck microspheres (featuring four broad emission bands) appeared in all three channels (Visualization 1). The use of different beads sizes provided us with a way to quantitatively validate the classification and the tracking results by their diffusion properties, as later explained.

In each frame of a given dataset (movie), ROIs suspected as containing a PSF were selected and the PSF type (color) was determined algorithmically based on the orientation of the brightest pixels. Next, the PSF was localized by maximum likelihood estimation, a detailed description is provided in the Methods section. Localization precision ranged between 10 nm to 30 nm depending on the brightness of each PSF. Since

an emitter can appear in more than one color channel and therefore have more than one associated PSF in the image, a combination step was performed to identify and classify individual beads based on position and correlation of motion.

Figure 2. Simultaneously imaged 3D positions of five species by multiplexed point-spread-function engineering. **(a)** Experimental image containing multiple PSFs. Each PSF encodes 3D position as well as color (indicated by the dotted box around it). The rectangle shows an improved contrast region containing three dim orange-channel beads. Scale bar = 20 μm . **(b)** 3D positions and colors of the beads from a. The diameters of the different bead types in the plot are based on manufacturer data (Table 1). The legend states the spectral emission peaks of the beads; TS = Tetraspeck. A description of bead types is in Table 1.

To demonstrate our system's ability to enable population-characterization, we next describe how we investigated the heterogeneity of the bead mixture. The trajectory of each bead was used to calculate the mean square displacement (MSD), which is characterized by the diffusion coefficient, D^{37} (Figure 3). The relation between D and the bead diameter is given by the Stokes-Einstein relation³⁸, stating an inverse relation between the two. Using the histograms of the diffusion coefficients per bead type, we found the mean bead size of each population in the suspension. Such characterization of bead sizes can be useful for inspecting mixtures of populations, or to simultaneously measure size distributions of multiple populations. Existing approaches for analyzing diffusion coefficients include dynamic light-scattering³⁹ (DLS) or nanoparticle tracking analysis⁴⁰ (NTA). Nanometer-resolution measurement of static particle sizes can also be done using an electron microscope, which involves significant experimental complexity and is typically not bio-compatible. All the mentioned approaches do not incorporate spectral information in the measurement.

Taking into considerations uncertainties in temperature and viscosity, the bead diameters obtained from the data were 105 ± 12 nm (yellow-green), 58 ± 7 nm (red), 211 ± 25 nm (crimson), 245 ± 24 nm (dark red) and 271 ± 32 nm (Tetraspeck). Some values are slightly higher than the manufacturer specifications (Table 1). We speculate that this is due to inter-bead interactions which could not be resolved based on spectral information alone.

Table 1. Bead specs according to manufacturer batch data

Bead name	Diameter (nm)	Peak emission wavelength (nm)
FluoSpheres Yellow-green (F8803, Invitrogen)	99 ± 7.8	515
FluoSpheres Red (F8793, Invitrogen)	46 ± 2	605
FluoSpheres Crimson (F8806, Invitrogen)	210 ± 11	645
FluoSpheres Dark red (F8807, Invitrogen)	220 ± 12	680
Tetraspeck (T7280, Invitrogen)	210 ± 10	430, 515, 580, 680

The details obtained in this complex environment can shed light on subtle interesting phenomena; we have observed a tendency of pairs of Tetraspeck beads to diffuse as a binary system, exhibiting highly correlated trajectories that maintain a relatively short distance of a few hundred nm. This is further discussed in the SI. We also encountered diffusers that are likely to be aggregates. This is supported by an increased brightness in addition to a lower-than-expected diffusion coefficient, but cannot be confirmed from the PSFs alone when the beads are of the same color, i.e. they are not optically resolvable. Larger aggregations of beads of the same type with more than twice the typical intensity and an exceptionally low diffusion coefficient were excluded from the statistics. Interestingly, some of the possible bead combinations, which would be readily identifiable by their spectrally unique combinations, were never observed: yellow-green and red, and yellow-green and dark red. Such interspecies interactions (e.g. binding and detaching frequencies) of spectrally distinct emitters can be dynamically explored at high resolution using our approach.

Figure 3. Simultaneously recorded trajectories of five bead populations. **(a)** Rendered 3D trajectories from a single time-lapse acquisition (Visualization 1). Color and axial position are represented by the trajectory color (brighter shades correspond to higher axial values). Beads are rendered as spheres at their position at the end of the timelapse, provided that they remained inside the FOV in the last frame. **(b)** Normalized histograms of the measured diffusion coefficients, per bead type (referred to by peak emission, in nm; TS = Tetraspeck). Total number of beads collected from multiple diffusion datasets are 29 (515), 30 (605), 19 (645), 75 (680), 19 (TS), collected from 16 recordings. **(c)** 3D plots of the beads marked by arrowheads in a, under uniform aspect ratio, for clarity. Gridlines are 2 μm apart in each axis.

To demonstrate the applicability of the method for multicolor imaging of a live biological system, we tracked fluorescently tagged DNA loci in *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* (SC) yeast cells (Figure 4). Two loci on both sides of the GAL locus were tagged¹⁰ using the Fluorescent Repressor Operator System (FROS) LacO-LacI-eGFP⁴¹ (green) and TetO-tetR-mCherry⁴² (red) (Figure 4.b). Their 3D motion was tracked, and their trajectories were extracted (Figure 4.c).

The intra-cellular imaging environment is more challenging than the suspended beads, as cellular background is present and the fluorescent proteins are subject to significant photobleaching. Adjusting to the experimental application, we designed new phase masks to produce PSFs optimized for a 2 μm axial range, using a pixel-wise optimization process⁴³, yielding PSFs with optimal 3D position encoding. The shallower depth of field provides compact PSFs, improving the signal to background ratio. The optimized PSFs resemble the Tetrapod, in a compact form compared to the 4-μm version. As before, they can also be rotated with respect to each other to enable simple spectral discrimination.

In addition to the two colors of the fluorescent proteins, red fluorescent beads were fixed to the coverslip to use as fiducial markers imaged in the red channel. In this channel, the 4- μm Tetrapod PSF was used to localize the bead in high resolution per frame, as the coverslip surface is expected to be $\sim 2\ \mu\text{m}$ below the loci in the nuclei. The purpose of the bead was two-fold: 1. To track sample drift during post-processing and 2. To correctly estimate the height of the nominal focal plane relative to the coverslip surface. The latter is highly important to create the correct optical model needed to localize emitters accurately^{43,44}.

In each frame of the timelapse movie, PSFs were fit similarly as described for the fluorescent beads, however with several additional parameters to account for an asymmetric Gaussian background originating from the cell²⁸. In each cell, the trajectories of the two loci were denoised by fitting a polynomial to the single-frame localized positions in time, per axis, to extract the dynamic distances between the loci. The experimental localization precision was estimated by the standard deviation of the fluctuations of the localizations around the smoothed trajectory. Fixed cells were used to verify that the high frequency position changes observed were due primarily to the finite localization precision. The calculated precision did not change significantly with the polynomial fit order, so long as the order was high enough to follow the low-frequency trends of the positions. We found a 12th order polynomial to be sufficient. From 28 cells analyzed, we measured a mean inter-loci distance of $282 \pm 93\ \text{nm}$, in agreement with previous measurements of this biological system¹⁰. The estimated 3D localization precision was $71 \pm 20\ \text{nm}$ for LacO, and $60 \pm 14\ \text{nm}$ for TetO. The reason for the better precision for TetO was that the cellular autofluorescence was stronger in the blue channel where LacO was localized.

Figure 4. In-vivo imaging of *S. Saccharomyces* DNA loci. **(a)** Cropped FOV of a frame from a time-lapse acquisition of live cells (Visualization 2). Top blow-up: enlarged ROI containing 6 cells (note that each cell appears duplicate, once in each spectral channel). Each cell contains 2 loci, observed as two PSFs. The emission in each channel is artificially colored depicting emission color. A double-sided arrow points at two PSFs from the same cell, for clarity. Bottom blow-up: the PSF of a dark-red fluorescent bead adhered to the coverslip. The PSF is artificially colored in enhanced contrast. The PSFs of the fluorescent loci are artificially colored depicting emission color, overlaid on a brightfield image of the cell, as seen captured through the optical system. The PSF of a red fiducial bead is also present in the FOV. **(b)** Labelling scheme of the yeast DNA. **(c)** Measured trajectories of the fluorescent loci in a single cell. Trajectories are generated from the polynomial fits shown in d-f. **(d-f)** Scatter plots of x,y,z localizations from the data used for c, green and red represent LacO and TetO respectively. Black lines show polynomial fits of the trajectory shown in c. Continuous line corresponds to LacO (green), and dashed line to TetO (red). The axial coordinates are relative to the coverslip surface.

In the cell imaging experiments, the signal was very well separated between the blue and orange channels. This was verified by imaging different strains of *S. Saccharomyces*, expressing only a single type of fluorescent protein (EGFP or mCherry). These measurements have shown that while some background is apparent in both channels, induced by the 488 nm laser excitation, there is no trace of localized signal from any loci in the other channel.

Discussion

Here, we have proposed an approach that overcomes the challenges of fast, multicolor, SPT by eliminating the tradeoff between acquiring spectral information, 3D spatial resolution, temporal resolution, and FOV size. As a proof of concept, we have demonstrated simultaneous, five-color tracking, limited by camera framerate (~50 Hz), with tens of nanometers precision, of >10 objects over a large FOV of $110 \times 70 \times 4 \mu\text{m}^3$. We applied our technique to characterize the 3D motions of fluorescent nanoparticles in vitro and in living biological samples, specifically, 3D tracking of fluorescently tagged DNA in live cells. The key advantage of our approach is that it harnesses an additional degree of freedom afforded by PSFE, namely uniquely encoding the color and position into the shape formed on the image, while maintaining a large field of view on a detector. This approach also alleviates the need for synchronized triggering of multiple detectors. Differing from our earlier implementation of single FOV, dual-color PSFE³², the multi-path design benefits from simpler DOE designs that are significantly more photon efficient and are designed to utilize various parts of the visible-NIR spectrum. Furthermore, the two approaches may be complementary – in principle, each spectral channel may include a multi-color phase-mask, further increasing the number of colors encoded in the system.

Advantageously, this multiplexed PSFE approach has the benefit from individually optimizing each path to meet specified requirements that can differ between the channels; for example, in the live-cell experiments we designed and used different PSF types were used for the DNA loci compared to the fiducial bead, suiting the different required z-ranges, a concept which has proven useful in 3D microscopy⁴⁵. Of particular potential interest is mapping the 2D information of spatially extended objects, e.g. cell membranes that are not suitable for 3D localization microscopy in one channel, while tracking individual particles in 3D.

One challenge of multicolor PSFE in general is capturing the positions of emitters that overlap both spatially and spectrally; while this remains a limitation in this approach as well, narrowing the individual transmitted spectral windows by filters or changing the fluorescent label can, to some extent, circumvent this issue. For sparse emitters, broad emission spectra can be used to exceed the number of physical spectral channels by using ratiometric spectral analysis to increase the number of distinguishable emitter types.

Future improvements to the optical setup and analysis pipeline can further increase the allowable density of emitters. For example, in the live-cell imaging experiments, where there is a known number of emitters

in a cell occupying an approximately known area, the configuration can be optimized to match the density of emitters and the spacing between channels to prevent PSF overlap of adjacent cells but minimize unnecessary gaps on the camera. Employing multi-emitter fitting algorithms can increase the allowable densities^{46,47}.

In conclusion, multiplexed PSFE provides a modular and photon-efficient solution for multicolor 3D localization with a large FOV. By simultaneously capturing the spectral information on a single camera, we anticipate this technique to be applicable to speed-necessitating experiments in challenging samples including in vivo imaging of fluorescent labels, and colocalization of objects in flow⁴⁸.

Methods

Localization, namely, determining the position of a particle given its measured PSF, was performed by fitting a model of the PSF to a region-of-interest (ROI). The model was derived from a phase-retrieved pupil function that is obtained by a vectorial implementation of phase retrieval (VIPR)⁴³. The parameter fitting is done using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) assuming Poisson photon statistics.

In the experiments performed here, the fitting procedure was divided into two scenarios based on the background intensity pattern. For imaging fluorescent beads diffusing in a water-glycerol mixture, the background was treated as a constant across the ROI. In this case, the fitted parameters were the 3D position (x, y, z), the total signal-photon counts detected from the emitter (N_{ph}), and the constant background photon count per pixel (b). When the background cannot be assumed constant inside the ROI, such as with cells that contain some autofluorescence, background-shape parameters must be added. In this case, a two-dimensional Gaussian background was added to the model, parameterized by the center position (x_g, y_g), the standard deviations in orthogonal directions (σ_x, σ_y), the angular tilt of the Gaussian (θ), and photon count (N_{ph-g}). To reduce the complexity of the fit function, the tilt angle and the constant background term were not fitted: the tilt angle per PSF is defined to be the same as the PSF orientation, due to the engineered PSF modifying the background emission as well, and the constant background is estimated from the ROI periphery.

Image registration was also performed as our imaging system effectively divides the emission light into three individual optical paths where the final images are overlaid on the detector with an intentional small

shift. The registration was done by imaging coverslip-adhered, multicolor fluorescent beads (Tetraspeck T7280, Invitrogen), which appear bright in all three channels. The three PSFs of each bead were localized, and a 3rd order, global-polynomial transformation was fitted to map the coordinate systems onto each other. To register the entire imaging volume, the microscope stage (or objective lens) was moved in all three dimensions, and multiple images are acquired (for more information see SI).

Throughout the experiments, we verified the stability of the registration by recording registration datasets before and after acquisition of the experimental data. In a post processing step, the correspondence between the registration functions from both datasets was checked to verify that the transformations generated before the experiment were still valid after the experiment.

All experiments were performed using an inverted microscope (Ti2 Eclipse, Nikon), equipped with a silicone-immersion objective (SR HP Plan Apo 100X/1.35 Sil λ S, Nikon). Images were captured using an sCMOS camera (Prime 95B, Teledyne Photometrics). In the diffusing beads experiment, excitation lasers were 488 nm and 532 nm, illuminating at optical densities of ~ 2.5 W/mm² each. In live-cell experiments, samples were illuminated with 488 nm, 561 nm and 640 nm light at low intensity of ~ 70 W/cm², ~ 160 W/cm², and 650 W/cm², respectively. The spectral channels of $\lambda < 567$ nm (blue), 567 nm $> \lambda < 635$ nm (orange) and $\lambda > 635$ nm (red) were set by longpass beamsplitters (Figure 1, S1) and were narrowed further with additional filters when necessary (see SI). In each channel, a photolithographically etched fused-silica dielectric phase mask was placed in the Fourier plane (Figure 1.c). The lenses of the 4-f system were of 200 mm focal length each, maintaining the magnification to the image.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

The supplementary information contains additional details on the experimental procedures, as well as the videos corresponding to the figures demonstrating the acquisition results.

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Authors Contribution

NO, BF and YS have conceived of the method; NO and LEW built the optical system; NO and YSE performed the experiments; YS and LEW provided suggestions and guidance throughout the work; RO fabricated the phase masks for all setups. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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Disclosures

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

- (1) Saxton, M. J.; Jacobson, K. SINGLE-PARTICLE TRACKING:Applications to Membrane Dynamics. *Annu. Rev. Biophys. Biomol. Struct.* **1997**, *26* (1), 373–399.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.biophys.26.1.373>.
- (2) Stracy, M.; Uphoff, S.; Garza de Leon, F.; Kapanidis, A. N. In Vivo Single-Molecule Imaging of Bacterial DNA Replication, Transcription, and Repair. *FEBS Lett.* **2014**, *588* (19), 3585–3594.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.febslet.2014.05.026>.

- (3) Dultz, E.; Tjong, H.; Weider, E.; Herzog, M.; Young, B.; Brune, C.; Müllner, D.; Loewen, C.; Alber, F.; Weis, K. Global Reorganization of Budding Yeast Chromosome Conformation in Different Physiological Conditions. *J. Cell Biol.* **2016**, *212* (3), 321–334.
<https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.201507069>.
- (4) Zhuang, X. Single-Molecule RNA Science. *Annu. Rev. Biophys. Biomol. Struct.* **2005**, *34* (1), 399–414. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.biophys.34.040204.144641>.
- (5) Helm, M.; Kobitski, A. Y.; Nienhaus, G. U. Single-Molecule Förster Resonance Energy Transfer Studies of RNA Structure, Dynamics and Function. *Biophys. Rev.* **2009**, *1* (4), 161–176.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12551-009-0018-3>.
- (6) Schuler, B.; Hofmann, H. Single-Molecule Spectroscopy of Protein Folding Dynamics—Expanding Scope and Timescales. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* **2013**, *23* (1), 36–47.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbi.2012.10.008>.
- (7) Fujiwara, T.; Ritchie, K.; Murakoshi, H.; Jacobson, K.; Kusumi, A. Phospholipids Undergo Hop Diffusion in Compartmentalized Cell Membrane. *J. Cell Biol.* **2002**, *157* (6), 1071–1081.
<https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.200202050>.
- (8) Bronshtein, I.; Kepten, E.; Kanter, I.; Berezin, S.; Lindner, M.; Redwood, A. B.; Mai, S.; Gonzalo, S.; Foisner, R.; Shav-Tal, Y.; Garini, Y. Loss of Lamin A Function Increases Chromatin Dynamics in the Nuclear Interior. *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms9044>.
- (9) Backlund, M. P.; Joyner, R.; Weis, K.; Moerner, W. E. Correlations of Three-Dimensional Motion of Chromosomal Loci in Yeast Revealed by the Double-Helix Point Spread Function Microscope. *Mol. Biol. Cell* **2014**, *25* (22), 3619–3629. <https://doi.org/10.1091/mbc.E14-06-1127>.
- (10) Shechtman, Y.; Gustavsson, A.-K.; Petrov, P. N.; Dultz, E.; Lee, M. Y.; Weis, K.; Moerner, W. E.

- Observation of Live Chromatin Dynamics in Cells via 3D Localization Microscopy Using Tetrapod Point Spread Functions. *Biomed. Opt. Express* **2017**, *8* (12), 5735.
<https://doi.org/10.1364/BOE.8.005735>.
- (11) Huisken, J. Optical Sectioning Deep Inside Live Embryos by Selective Plane Illumination Microscopy. *Science (80-.)*. **2004**, *305* (5686), 1007–1009.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1100035>.
- (12) Ritter, J. G.; Veith, R.; Veenendaal, A.; Siebrasse, J. P.; Kubitscheck, U. Light Sheet Microscopy for Single Molecule Tracking in Living Tissue. *PLoS One* **2010**, *5* (7), e11639.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0011639>.
- (13) Jonkman, J.; Brown, C. M.; Cole, R. W. *Quantitative Confocal Microscopy. Beyond a Pretty Picture*, 1st ed.; Elsevier Inc., 2014; Vol. 123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-420138-5.00007-0>.
- (14) Shtengel, G.; Galbraith, J. A.; Galbraith, C. G.; Lippincott-Schwartz, J.; Gillette, J. M.; Manley, S.; Sougrat, R.; Waterman, C. M.; Kanchanawong, P.; Davidson, M. W.; Fetter, R. D.; Hess, H. F. Interferometric Fluorescent Super-Resolution Microscopy Resolves 3D Cellular Ultrastructure. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **2009**, *106* (9), 3125–3130. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0813131106>.
- (15) Huang, F.; Sirinakis, G.; Allgeyer, E. S.; Schroeder, L. K.; Duim, W. C.; Kromann, E. B.; Phan, T.; Rivera-Molina, F. E.; Myers, J. R.; Irnov, I.; Lessard, M.; Zhang, Y.; Handel, M. A.; Jacobs-Wagner, C.; Lusk, C. P.; Rothman, J. E.; Toomre, D.; Booth, M. J.; Bewersdorf, J. Ultra-High Resolution 3D Imaging of Whole Cells. *Cell* **2016**, *166* (4), 1028–1040.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2016.06.016>.
- (16) Dalgarno, P. A.; Dalgarno, H. I. C.; Putoud, A.; Lambert, R.; Paterson, L.; Logan, D. C.; Towers, D. P.; Warburton, R. J.; Greenaway, A. H. Multiplane Imaging and Three Dimensional Nanoscale

- Particle Tracking in Biological Microscopy. *Opt. Express* **2010**, *18* (2), 877.
<https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.18.000877>.
- (17) Abrahamsson, S.; Chen, J.; Hajj, B.; Stallinga, S.; Katsov, A. Y.; Wisniewski, J.; Mizuguchi, G.; Soule, P.; Mueller, F.; Darzacq, C. D.; Darzacq, X.; Wu, C.; Bargmann, C. I.; Agard, D. A.; Dahan, M.; Gustafsson, M. G. L. Fast Multicolor 3D Imaging Using Aberration-Corrected Multifocus Microscopy. *Nat. Methods* **2013**, *10* (1), 60–63. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2277>.
- (18) Ram, S.; Kim, D.; Ober, R. J.; Ward, E. S. 3D Single Molecule Tracking with Multifocal Plane Microscopy Reveals Rapid Intercellular Transferrin Transport at Epithelial Cell Barriers. *Biophys. J.* **2012**, *103* (7), 1594–1603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpj.2012.08.054>.
- (19) Balzarotti, F.; Eilers, Y.; Gwosch, K. C.; Gynnå, A. H.; Westphal, V.; Stefani, F. D.; Elf, J.; Hell, S. W. Nanometer Resolution Imaging and Tracking of Fluorescent Molecules with Minimal Photon Fluxes. *Science (80-.)*. **2017**, *355* (6325), 606–612. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aak9913>.
- (20) Wehnekamp, F.; Plucińska, G.; Thong, R.; Misgeld, T.; Lamb, D. C. Nanoresolution Real-Time 3D Orbital Tracking for Studying Mitochondrial Trafficking in Vertebrate Axons in Vivo. *Elife* **2019**, *8*. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.46059>.
- (21) Gwosch, K. C.; Pape, J. K.; Balzarotti, F.; Hoess, P.; Ellenberg, J.; Ries, J.; Hell, S. W. MINFLUX Nanoscopy Delivers 3D Multicolor Nanometer Resolution in Cells. *Nat. Methods* **2020**, *17* (2), 217–224. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0688-0>.
- (22) Pavani, S. R. P.; Thompson, M. A.; Biteen, J. S.; Lord, S. J.; Liu, N.; Twieg, R. J.; Piestun, R.; Moerner, W. E. Three-Dimensional, Single-Molecule Fluorescence Imaging beyond the Diffraction Limit by Using a Double-Helix Point Spread Function. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **2009**, *106* (9), 2995–2999. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0900245106>.

- (23) Shechtman, Y.; Sahl, S. J.; Backer, A. S.; Moerner, W. E. Optimal Point Spread Function Design for 3D Imaging. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2014**, *113* (13), 133902.
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.113.133902>.
- (24) Von Diezmann, A.; Shechtman, Y.; Moerner, W. E. Three-Dimensional Localization of Single Molecules for Super-Resolution Imaging and Single-Particle Tracking. *Chemical Reviews*. 2017, pp 7244–7275. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.6b00629>.
- (25) Ober, R. J.; Ram, S.; Ward, E. S. Localization Accuracy in Single-Molecule Microscopy. *Biophys. J.* **2004**, *86* (2), 1185–1200. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3495\(04\)74193-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3495(04)74193-4).
- (26) Mortensen, K. I.; Churchman, L. S.; Spudich, J. A.; Flyvbjerg, H. Optimized Localization Analysis for Single-Molecule Tracking and Super-Resolution Microscopy. *Nat. Methods* **2010**, *7* (5), 377–381.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.1447>.
- (27) Rieger, B.; Stallinga, S. The Lateral and Axial Localization Uncertainty in Super-Resolution Light Microscopy. *ChemPhysChem* **2014**, *15* (4), 664–670. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cphc.201300711>.
- (28) Shechtman, Y.; Gustavsson, A.-K.; Petrov, P. N.; Dultz, E.; Lee, M. Y.; Weis, K.; Moerner, W. E. Observation of Live Chromatin Dynamics in Cells via 3D Localization Microscopy Using Tetrapod Point Spread Functions. *Biomed. Opt. Express* **2017**, *8* (12), 5735.
<https://doi.org/10.1364/BOE.8.005735>.
- (29) Gregor, I.; Butkevich, E.; Enderlein, J.; Mojiri, S. Instant Three Color Multi-Plane Fluorescence Microscopy. *bioRxiv* **2021**. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.05.07.443091>.
- (30) Zhang, Z.; Kenny, S. J.; Hauser, M.; Li, W.; Xu, K. Ultrahigh-Throughput Single-Molecule Spectroscopy and Spectrally Resolved Super-Resolution Microscopy. Supplement. *Nat. Methods* **2015**, *12* (10), 935–938. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.3528>.

- (31) Song, K.-H.; Zhang, Y.; Brenner, B.; Sun, C.; Zhang, H. F. Symmetrically Dispersed Spectroscopic Single-Molecule Localization Microscopy. *Light Sci. Appl.* **2020**, *9* (1), 92.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41377-020-0333-9>.
- (32) Shechtman, Y.; Weiss, L. E.; Backer, A. S.; Lee, M. Y.; Moerner, W. E. Multicolour Localization Microscopy by Point-Spread-Function Engineering. *Nat. Photonics* **2016**, *10* (9), 590–594.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nphoton.2016.137>.
- (33) Jesacher, A.; Bernet, S.; Ritsch-Marte, M. Colour Hologram Projection with an SLM by Exploiting Its Full Phase Modulation Range. *Opt. Express* **2014**, *22* (17), 20530–20541.
<https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.22.020530>.
- (34) Smith, C.; Huisman, M.; Siemons, M.; Grünwald, D.; Stallinga, S. Simultaneous Measurement of Emission Color and 3D Position of Single Molecules. *Opt. Express* **2016**, *24* (5), 4996.
<https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.24.004996>.
- (35) Grover, G.; Quirin, S.; Fiedler, C.; Piestun, R. Photon Efficient Double-Helix PSF Microscopy with Application to 3D Photo-Activation Localization Imaging. *Biomed. Opt. Express* **2011**, *2* (11), 3010.
<https://doi.org/10.1364/BOE.2.003010>.
- (36) Shechtman, Y.; Sahl, S. J.; Backer, A. S.; Moerner, W. E. Optimal Point Spread Function Design for 3D Imaging. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2014**, *113* (13), 133902.
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.113.133902>.
- (37) Michalet, X.; Berglund, A. J. Optimal Diffusion Coefficient Estimation in Single-Particle Tracking. *Phys. Rev. E* **2012**, *85* (6), 061916. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.85.061916>.
- (38) Einstein, A. Über Die von Der Molekularkinetischen Theorie Der Wärme Geforderte Bewegung von in Ruhenden Flüssigkeiten Suspendierten Teilchen. *Ann. Phys.* **1905**, *322* (8), 549–560.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.19053220806>.

- (39) Carpenter, D. K. Dynamic Light Scattering with Applications to Chemistry, Biology, and Physics (Berne, Bruce J.; Pecora, Robert). *J. Chem. Educ.* **1977**, *54* (10), A430.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/ed054pA430.1>.
- (40) Dragovic, R. A.; Gardiner, C.; Brooks, A. S.; Tannetta, D. S.; Ferguson, D. J. P.; Hole, P.; Carr, B.; Redman, C. W. G.; Harris, A. L.; Dobson, P. J.; Harrison, P.; Sargent, I. L. Sizing and Phenotyping of Cellular Vesicles Using Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis. *Nanomedicine Nanotechnology, Biol. Med.* **2011**, *7* (6), 780–788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nano.2011.04.003>.
- (41) Straight, A. F.; Belmont, A. S.; Robinett, C. C.; Murray, A. W. GFP Tagging of Budding Yeast Chromosomes Reveals That Protein–Protein Interactions Can Mediate Sister Chromatid Cohesion. *Curr. Biol.* **1996**, *6* (12), 1599–1608. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0960-9822\(02\)70783-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0960-9822(02)70783-5).
- (42) Michaelis, C.; Ciosk, R.; Nasmyth, K. Cohesins: Chromosomal Proteins That Prevent Premature Separation of Sister Chromatids. *Cell* **1997**, *91* (1), 35–45. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0092-8674\(01\)80007-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0092-8674(01)80007-6).
- (43) Ferdman, B.; Nehme, E.; Weiss, L. E.; Orange, R.; Alalouf, O.; Shechtman, Y. VIPR: Vectorial Implementation of Phase Retrieval for Fast and Accurate Microscopic Pixel-Wise Pupil Estimation. *Opt. Express* **2020**, *28* (7), 10179. <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.388248>.
- (44) Petrov, P. N.; Moerner, W. E. Addressing Systematic Errors in Axial Distance Measurements in Single-Emitter Localization Microscopy. *Opt. Express* **2020**, *28* (13), 18616.
<https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.391496>.
- (45) Gustavsson, A.; Petrov, P. N.; Lee, M. Y.; Shechtman, Y.; Moerner, W. E. 3D Single-Molecule Super-Resolution Microscopy with a Tilted Light Sheet. *Nat. Commun.* **2018**, *9* (1), 123.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02563-4>.

- (46) Nehme, E.; Freedman, D.; Gordon, R.; Ferdman, B.; Weiss, L. E.; Alalouf, O.; Naor, T.; Orange, R.; Michaeli, T.; Shechtman, Y. DeepSTORM3D: Dense 3D Localization Microscopy and PSF Design by Deep Learning. *Nat. Methods* **2020**, *17* (7), 734–740. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-020-0853-5>.
- (47) Artur Speiser, Lucas-Raphael Müller, Ulf Matti, Christopher J. Obara, Wesley R. Legant, Anna Kreshuk, Jakob H. Macke, Jonas Ries, S. C. T. Deep Learning Enables Fast and Dense Single-Molecule Localization with High Accuracy. *bioRxiv* **2020**.
<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.10.26.355164v1>
- (48) Weiss, L. E.; Shalev Ezra, Y.; Goldberg, S.; Ferdman, B.; Adir, O.; Schroeder, A.; Alalouf, O.; Shechtman, Y. Three-Dimensional Localization Microscopy in Live Flowing Cells. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2020**, *15* (6), 500–506. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-020-0662-0>.

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